

Analysis of energy, CO2 emissions and economy of the technological migration for clean cooking in Ecuador

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Highlights

- Ecuador is implementing the National Efficient Cooking Program
- Technological migration from gas to electric stoves has been analyzed
- Energetic, economical and indoor air quality aspects have been considered
- Business as usual and new policies scenarios for 2022 have been evaluated
- The application of the new policies NECP is energetic and economically feasible

Abstract —

The objective of this study is to analyze the application of the National Efficient Cooking Program (NECP) in Ecuador, which aims to migrate from Liquefied Petroleum Gas based stoves to induction stoves. The NECP objective is to minimize fossil fuels uses and to reduce LPG subsidy. Typical Ecuadorian meals have been cooked and monitored to accomplish the analysis on CO₂ and CO emissions, time and energy consumption in an induction stove, LPG based stove and electric coil stove. The present scenario has been compared with a business as usual scenario and a future scenario in 2022, when it is expected that 83,61% of the Ecuadorian electricity will be generated by hydroelectric power plants, and the LPG gas bottle should not be further subsidized. The study exposes how induction stoves are also more efficient in terms of government costs, time energy consumption and the reduction of CO₂ and CO emissions during the cooking process. Finally, this new policy, which considers the technological migration from cooking based on imported fossil fuels to a more efficient cooking facility based on locally produced electric energy, is a viable alternative to the end of the subsidy on LPG.

Keywords – Household cooking, energy efficiency, induction stove, Ecuador, National Efficient Cooking Program (NECP).

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1. Introduction.

Energy efficiency is considered one of the most cost effective ways to enhance security of energy supply and reduce greenhouse gas emissions, as well as other pollutants (Jaffe and Stavins, 1994). Energy has always been one of the crucial issues a country has to deal with (Asif and Muneer, 2007). To decree appropriate policies and regulations in the energy sector results in a positive impact on the economic stability of a country, while improper policies as a result of inefficiencies in the economy will bring a country into high economic costs (Travezan et al., 2013). However, migrations from conventional to more efficient technologies involve a complex process. It is necessary to focus on proper planning and employing appropriate policies to ensure that migration produces a positive impact on the population and government (Milne and Boardman, 2000). Several aspects and influencing parameters on the total outcome of an energy system need to be considered from both sides, in order to estimate the improvements in energy efficiency (Pérez-Lombard et al., 2008).

Within this context, the General Assembly of the United Nations (UN) has declared 2014-2024 the “Decade of Sustainable Energy for All”. This resolution tries to improve the statistics about 1.3 billion people worldwide who still live without electricity, and that more than 2.6 billion people rely on traditional biomass for cooking and heating (Smith, 2014). In order to achieve the UN’s goal, the Ecuadorian government is intended to provide universal access to electricity and clean cooking facilities using electricity to all the habitants of the country (Martínez-Gómez et al., 2016).

Several studies have been performed on clean cooking facilities using electricity. In this regard, it has been observed that electric coil stoves have low efficiency and high power consumption, so they are not a good option to be consider in policies for an efficient cooking facility (Smith & Sagar, 2014). In the case of induction stoves seem to be a better option, because they present a higher energy efficiency . and several advantages in comparison to traditional stoves as: i) energy efficiency, ii) enhanced safety, iii) no waste of energy when cookware is removed from the hob, iv) automatic cut–off function in case of overheating, and v) no emission of harmful flue gases (Wong, 2013) and usually uses electricity produced in the country (Villacís et al., 2015).

In the case of cooking with electricity, it has been observed that in areas where power supply is available, special electrical appliances such as electric kettles, rice stoves, ovens and microwaves are also used and lead to a reduction of biomass used for cooking in an effective way (Smith & Sagar, 2014). Recently, India (Himachal Pradesh) started to develop a program on “access to clean cooking alternatives in rural India”. In nearly 4000 rural households induction stoves were introduced to improve clean cooking facilities, as

part of this program (Banerjee et al., 2016). Although, it is not a country-wide program, the availability of inexpensive portable induction cooking stoves is shifting the balance towards cooking with electricity. This program is mainly happening in cities because of electricity costs and power availability, but these constraints are changing as electrification expands and prices for induction stoves fall (Smith et al., 2014). In the case of Ecuador the National Efficient Cooking Program (NECP) is being projected across the whole country and the first step has been achieved, improving the electric grid (CONELEC, 2015).

The NECP aims to migrate from around three millions Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) based stoves to induction stoves, being the first energy policy program to introduce the idea of more efficient cooking facilities at a national level in a country (MEER, 2013), (Villacís et al., 2015). In this way Ecuador is replacing the use of fossil fuels in its energy mix to renewable energies, investing 11619 Mus \$ in a new hydroelectric power station, and a new electric grid transmission infrastructure, which is expected to be finished in 2022 (CONELEC, 2013).

The NECP objective is to minimize fossil fuels uses and import and to reduce LPG subsidy. Until now the government of Ecuador subsidizes the LPG for the population: 15 kg of bottled LPG costs 1,60 us\$ for the user, while in neighbor countries (Peru and Colombia) this price is on average thirteen times higher (17 us\$ and 23 us\$) (Riofrio, 2015). The total cost of this subsidy for the country is about 690 Mus\$ per year, and the total cost caused by smuggling lays around 20 %. In addition, about 78% of the domestic demand for bottled LPG is imported, which creates a major dependency and therefore a significant outflow of national funds abroad, that considerably affects the balance of trade in Ecuador (CONELEC, 2013). So the government's aim is to increment local electricity production through new hydropower infrastructure, to partly sustain the national cooking energy consumption and displace in this manner imported and subsidized LPG consumption.

The NECP is also related with the idea of clean cooking, so the reduction of harmful gases emissions in the kitchen. Several programs have been developed in order to improve clean cooking in China (Sinton et al., 2004), Africa, (Kumar et al., 2014), India (Pohekar et al., 2005) and Burkina Faso (Ouedraogo et al., 2006). These programs usually introduce better stoves in rural households with more efficient biomass stoves at the beginning, improved coal stoves later and improved LPG stoves in these days (Sinton et al., 2004), (Shrimali, 2011). The reason for the implementation of these programs has been mainly because people stopped using stoves based on solid fuels with poor combustion, low energy efficiency and that also produces harmful smoke that mainly affects the female and children population, which are most of the time with their mothers during their first years. Another reason to develop these programs is that about 25% of outdoor particle pollution emissions, and significant contributions to CO₂ and shorter-lived greenhouse pollutants, can be accounted to the incomplete combustion, and poor energy efficiency, characterizing biomass combustion (Smith et al., 2005), (Chafeetal et al., 2014). With 3.9 million premature deaths annually around the world, traditional uses of biomass cooking fuels are now understood to be the largest single environmental health threat in the world, although they only affect about 40% of the world's population (Smith et al., 2014).

Related with this idea, several investigations have been performed, in order to evaluate the reduction of greenhouse gases and concentration of carcinogenic compound emissions in different types of stoves during cooking (Shen et al., 2011). Indoor levels of particles in overdeveloped countries are much lower than in the so called developing countries, and this is generally attributable to the advancement in technology for general household cooking activities, as the use of cleaner fuels (such as LPG, electricity and

natural gas), for cooking and heating (Shen et al., 2011), (Zhao et al., 2014) instead of traditional biomass.

One of the most dangerous gases studied in these researches is carbon (Shen et al., 2011), (Zhao et al., 2014). Furthermore, potential sources inside a building that may generate carbon monoxide include gas heating systems such as gas stoves and gas water heaters, also cigarette smoke, and portable kerosene heaters. Levels of CO higher than 5 ppm indicate the presence of exhaust gases in the indoor environment and should be investigated. Levels of carbon monoxide inside buildings should not exceed 9 or 10 ppm (ASHRAE, 2001), (ANSI/ASHRAE, 2004). Another dangerous gas evaluated is carbon dioxide. The carbon dioxide level is usually greater inside a building than outside, even in buildings with few complaints about indoor air quality. Properly ventilated buildings should have CO₂ levels between 600 ppm and 1000 ppm (Indoor Air Quality Standard of China GB/T 18883, 2002).

In order to evaluate the impact of the NECP as first country program of energy efficiency and clean cooking using electric induction stoves, this study shows a comparative analysis of LPG, electrical coil and induction stoves has been realized measuring cooking time, energy consumption and concentrations of CO and CO₂ during cooking six typical meals of the Ecuadorian cuisine. The economic costs of the current subsidies for LPG and electricity for cooking have been evaluated and compared with future scenarios based on business as usual and new policies for 2022. In addition, the costs perceived by the user and the energy consumption in this technological migration, are detailed studied and presented.

2. Experimental method

2.1. Site selection

The tests were performed in the culinary laboratories of the International University of Ecuador (UIDE), situated in Quito the capital of Ecuador. Quito is located at about 2800 meters above sea level, therefore it is a representative place to study the indoor environment in an Andean region during cooking. The study has been developed without air pollution sources close to the experimental area. A schema of the kitchen where the tests were performed is shown in Fig. 1. The exterior windows and doors in the kitchen remained closed during the test. The reason to close the windows and the door is to assure the accurate measurement of the pollutant concentration in the case – study kitchen. The lower edge of the hood of the case-study stove is set at a height of 1.8 m from the floor. The hood is commercially available in the market and has a volume flow rate of 1,2 m³/s.

Figure 1. Layout of the case-study kitchen with location of the measurement points.

2.2 Case-study meals

The food prepared in this study included the most representative meals in Quito. The selected meals were chicken broth, cheese and potato soup, quinoa soup, barley rice soup, boiled rice and French fries. The quantity of the ingredients was determined to serve a lunch for a family of four members. Achiote and olive oils were used as cooking oil. All ingredients and condiments were purchased from a local supermarket, and the amounts used were measured by an Ohaus Ranger Count 3000 Compact bench counting. In order to achieve the most appropriate consistency, the tests were repeated three times for each meal. Detailed information of each meal regarding ingredients, quantity and treatment is presented in Appendix 1.

2.3 Instruments

To perform the experiments three types of stoves were used. The first one was an induction stove; Teka IRS 643 of 7400 W, with 4 induction zones, one of them with 3200 W of maximum power. The second one was an electric coil stove; GE JP-200-OP1-WH of 900 W, with 2 heating zones. The final one was an industrial LPG stove; SILKO ECG74E of 15000 W, with 4 stove burners. As the LPG stove is an industrial equipment, the power of the stove burners were limited to 3200 W during the test, in order to simulate a domestic kitchen and have the same thermal power induction.

The induction stove was connected in series with the electric grid and an electricity quality analyzer Fluke 43 TF II. The electric coil stove was connected in series with the electric grid and with the analyzer Sentron PAC3200 of Siemens. Through those devices, electrical grid parameters such as instantaneous power and power curve were measured.

In all three cases, a flue gas analyzer complete mobile unit for emission control (Brain Bee Au Mobile) was used to measure the indoor CO and CO₂ concentrations. The range of CO₂ measurement is from 0 ppm to 15000 ppm with an accuracy of 1 ppm, and the response time is 1 s. The range of CO measurement is from 0 ppm to 500 ppm with an accuracy of 0,01 ppm, and the response time is 1 s.

The following experiments were conducted using the observational method applied to one kind of induction pot, one induction pan made of AISI 304 stainless steel in its body, and AISI 430 stainless steel in its bottom, which is the normal configuration of induction cookware. Each cookware was covered with an AISI 304 stainless steel lid during the tests.

2.4 Procedure

2.4.1 Concentration of CO and CO₂ test procedure

To measure the concentration of CO and CO₂ the studies procedure followed several steps: first, the interior door and the exterior window remained closed throughout the study. Secondly the exhaust hood was turned on. After ten seconds, the gas analyzer was placed at 140 cm high, which is the common breathing zone of a female cook in Ecuador. Then, the CO and CO₂ indoor background levels of the kitchen were measured for a period of time of 30 s for every meal. At last, the cooking of the six case-study meals started, and the air concentrations of CO and CO₂ continued to be measured. Between each test, the CO and CO₂ concentrations were measured, to reach the initial level.

2.4.2 Procedure to measure the energetic consumption in stoves

For electric measurements in the electric coil and induction stoves, the Fluke 430 TF II and the analyzer Sentron PAC3200 of Siemens were placed on the wires of the electric grid. Temperature of the food and cooking time were measured too.

For the LPG based stove, the weight of the bottled gas was measured before, during, and after the cooking procedure. To determine the energy of LPG, 15,11 kWh/kg as heat of combustion were considered, corresponding Quitos gas distributor.

2.4.3 Production of primary energy into electricity

To conduct the economic analysis, first the quantity of primary energy used in the electricity mix was determined. The electricity generation data for 2014 was taken as a base line, this data was acquired from the publication of the Ecuadorian electricity sector database, “Agencia de Control y Regulación de la Electricidad” (ARCONEL, 2014). Using this data, a detailed analysis of every renewable and not renewable energy source was calculated, with the purpose to determine the amount of energy generated and its contribution in the entire production. Applying the equation (1) (Secretaria General, 2012) the primary energy consumption for electricity generation for 2014 was determined.

$$Pe = \sum Edel,i * Cf,deli \quad (1)$$

Where Pe is primary energy, $Edel,i$ is the energy produced, including renewable and not renewable sources, and $Cf,deli$ is the conversion factor to primary energy. This factor is particular for each energy source. In order to determine the Conversion factors (Cf) to Primary energy (Pe), the suggested values by the Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía of Spain (IDAE, 2011) were used. Table 1 shows the obtained values of primary energy for the generated electricity mix in Ecuador for 2014.

In addition, a future scenario has been considered for 2022, as Ecuador is changing its energy mix in the next 6 years. The government’s ambition for 2022 is that the main source of electricity generation will be obtained from hydropower plants. The projection data of the generation expansion Electrification Master Plan 2013-2022 (CONELEC, 2013) of this future scenario were derived, where thermoelectric generation is almost halved and hydroelectric is triplicated. In Table 1 electricity generation and conversion to primary energy sources for 2014 and 2022 is disaggregated presented. The same conversion factors of primary energy in 2014 and 2022 have been used. It is expected that

energy production will be increased by 29,09 %, while thermoelectric generation will decrease g by 48,03 %, between both scenarios.

Table 1. Primary energy for electric generation for 2014 and 2022

	Current situation (2014)				Future scenery (2022)			
	Energy [MWh]	%	Cf to Pe	Pe [MWh]	Energy [MWh]	%	Cf to Pe	Pe [MWh]
Biomass Gen.	399471,18	1,64	3,03	1210397,68				
Solar Gen.	16482,7	0,07	1	16482,70				
Eolic Gen.	79742,47	0,33	1	79742,47				
Total Renewable Gen.	495696,35	2,04	*2,64	1306622,85	553000	1,30	*2,64	1457671,50
Hydroelectric Gen.	11457895,63	47,14	1	11457895,63	35729000	83,67	1	35729000
Fuel oil Gen.	5483600,39	22,56	2,54	13928344,99				
Gas natural Gen	2964552,66	12,20	1,012	3000127,29				
Diesel Gen.	2759169,02	11,35	2,54	7008289,32				
Crude oil Gen.	1146299,29	4,72	2,54	2911600,21				
Total Thermoelectric Gen.	12353621,36	50,82	*2,17	26848361,81	6420000	15,03	*2,17	13952708,90
		Total	*1,63	39612880,29			*1,20	51139380,40

* weighted arithmetic mean

2.4.4 Micro and Macroeconomic Scenarios

The economic incidences on users and on the finances of the Ecuadorian government were analyzed to measure the impact of the NECP in Ecuador. For this purpose, the energy subsidies for cooking in 2014 and in the future 2022 have been considered. Currently, the prices of the user's electricity bill do not represent the actual cost. This is because prices are influenced by the direct and indirect subsidies that were implemented in the past, as part of state policy to fossil fuels, accounting for 50.82 % of the electricity generation in Ecuador (Table 1).

- I. **Currently situation:** The bottled gas of 15 kg LPG is subsidized in Ecuador and costs 1,60 us\$ at a local distribution store. Meanwhile, the cost of the LPG bottled gas without subsidies is about 20,00 us\$. This is an average value between prices of neighbor countries such as Peru and Colombia, where the price for a bottled gas lays on 17 us\$ and 23 us\$ respectively (Riofrio, 2015). The cost of subsidized electricity for the user in Ecuador nowadays is 0,092 us\$ / kWh, based on data from (ARCONEL, 2014). Meanwhile, the cost of the electricity to the Ecuadorian government is 0,162 us\$ / kWh (CONELEC, 2015). This variation on the price of the electric energy is explained by the subsidies to the fossil fuels, that were up to 1016 Mus\$ in 2014 (CONELEC, 2013). Moreover, according to the "Plan Efficient Cooking", end users will have a 100 % subsidy for the first 80 kWh consumed, and a rate of 0,092 us\$ / kWh for further kWh consumption (MEER, 2013).
- II. **2022 situation:** LPG bottled gas of 15 kg is not subsidized, and the user pays about 20,00 us\$, as it has been explained in the current situation scenario. Based on data from (ARCONEL, 2014), it is estimated that the cost of electricity to the Ecuadorian user will be 0,0858 us\$ / kWh,. Meanwhile, the cost of the electricity to the Ecuadorian government will be 0,0615 us\$ / kWh, as according to the prediction published by (CONELEC, 2013). In 2022, the subsidies to the fossil

fuels for the electricity sector are expected to lay around 34 Mus\$ (CONELEC, 2013). In addition, according to the NECP, end users will receive a subsidy of 58 % for the first 80 kWh. Therefore the expenses will be 0,04 us\$ / kWh, and the projected expenses for the extra consumption of electricity would be 0,0615 us\$ / kWh (MEER, 2013).

To evaluate the potential benefits of the massive introduction of induction stoves in Ecuador, the current and two future scenarios have been considered. The first scenario is a business as usual (BAU) by 2022, in which there are no active policies to replace LPG to induction stoves. The second scenario considers the new policies and regulations in the context of NECP for 2022, which seek a massive replacement of LPG to induction stoves. For 2022, both scenarios are considered national policies, in course with the penetration of hydroelectric energy, according to the Electrification Master Plan 2013-2022 (CONELEC, 2013). The detailed considerations for each scenario are following:

- I. **Current situation:** For this scenario according to the Ministry of industries (MIPRO in Ecuador), 50000 induction stoves were sold until December 2014 (MIPRO, 2015), and data from the national census performed in 2010 was used. As reported by this source, 3407375 households used LPG as fuel for cooking (Riofrio, 2015). The current subsidizes have been considered.
- II. **BAU2022:** The technology migration policy of the NECP is discarded. An estimation of the number of LPG based and of induction stoves within the increase of the population in 2022 has been considered, according to the population growth projection from the Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censos (INEC), which also contemplates a reduction in the number of family members per household to 2022 (INEC, 2010). The introduction of hydroelectric power plants is considered, maintaining present costs of LPG, and increasing the costs of electricity to the user, up to 0,0858 us\$/kWh.
- III. **New Polices 2022:** For this scenario, it is estimated that 4688795 induction stoves will be introduced in 2022. According to the context of the NECP, based on the population growth projection, and the projection of the number of people by family in Ecuador (CONELEC, 2013).

3 Results

3.1. Emission of CO and CO₂

The results of concentrations of CO and CO₂ of LPG cooking are represented in figure 2, and for electric stoves (coil and induction) in figure 3. For LPG cooking it is found that as soon as it is turned on, and water or oil is added to the pot (steps 1 and 2, Appendix 2), the concentration of CO and CO₂ increases strongly at each meal, despite using the hood continuously. The concentration of CO varies strongly when frying oil or boiling water. The CO concentration exceeds the acceptable limit of 10 ppm when cooking meals like roast beef (Quinoa Barley and rice soup), or when frying throughout the process as in the case of the French fries. On the other hand, the cheese and potato soup with fried vegetables and other dishes that do not use oil (boiled rice and chicken broth), show values of concentrations of CO that are below 10 ppm.

Figure 2. a) Variation of CO and b) CO₂ emission during cooking in a LPG stove.

CO₂ emission increases its concentration in the early stages too, but there is no relation with a frying or boiling process. The CO₂ level increases in the case of barley rice soup up to 11000 ppm, where it remains during most of the cooking process. A similar behavior is observed when frying French fries, which maintains CO₂ emissions of 9000 ppm throughout the process. In the case of cheese/potato and quinoa soup, there are initial values exceeding 4000 ppm and 3000 ppm of CO₂ respectively, but these emissions decrease below 1000 ppm after 1000 s of cooking time. The two dishes that do not use oil (boiled rice and chicken broth), maintain a very uniform CO₂ concentration throughout the process, with values in the range of 4000-3000 ppm. In all experimental cases, CO₂ concentration exceeded the recommended limit of 1000 ppm (ANSI/ASHRAE, 2004), (ASHRAE, 2001), (Indoor Air Quality Standard of China GB/T 18883, 2002). The only exception where ppm values do not exceed recommended values, are the last cooking stage of cheese/ potato and quinoa soup.

Figure 3 represent the emission of CO and CO₂ when cooking French fries with electric coil and induction stoves. It is observed that throughout the cooking process the recommended limit of CO and CO₂ emissions are not exceeded. Additionally, the CO and CO₂ emissions in the electric coil stove were nearly double as high in comparison with the induction emissions.

3.2. Energy consumption of the stoves

Figure 4 shows the energy consumed for cooking six meals in the LPG, electric coil and induction stoves. The first feature to notice is that the electric coil stove retains much less power than the other two stoves, which leads to require a longer cooking time. This happens because the electric coil stove has a 900 W peak power, compared with the 3200 W peak power of the induction and LPG stoves. We observe that the induction stove does not reach its maximum power capacity. This relies on the interest of the Ecuadorian government, of only using the average power consumption, instead the maximum power capacity of induction stoves, in order to calculate the impact of the "efficient cooking program" on the electric grid. Additionally, the power/heat variation of the induction stove during cooking is uneven or rugged in comparison with LPG or electric coil stoves, according to the experience of the chefs.

The time and energy consumed during the cooking process of six experimental meals with three different technologies are presented in Table 2. The induction stove turns out to be the fastest cooking stove for all meals, followed by the LPG stove and the electric coil stove. Furthermore, induction stove cooking consumes less energy in all the experimental meals.

Table 2. Cooking time and energy consumption of meals with the three technologies

Dishes	Time induction stove [s]	Time in electric coil stove [s]	Time LPG stove [s]	Energy consumption induction stove [kWh]	Energy consumption electric coil stove [kWh]	Energy consumption LPG stove [kWh]
Chicken broth	4875	7358	5540	0,98	1,03	3,07
Cheese and potato soup	2845	3825	3475	0,83	1,3	3,20
Quinoa soup	2525	5840	3230	0,59	0,78	2,95
Barley rice soup	1820	4775	2645	0,68	1,72	3,01
White rice	1245	3120	2073	0,45	0,81	2,15
French fries	805	2680	1080	0,29	0,51	1,26

To assess the energy costs spent in cooking activities of a representative Ecuadorian family, a daily consumption of 3,2 kWh, and a monthly power consumption of 96 kWh

for an induction stove kitchen have been considered. This data is based on the monitoring carried out for an average Ecuadorian family during a month (Riofrio, 2015). If the six dishes analyzed in this study represent a normal daily diet of an Ecuadorian family, the sum of the energy consumption of induction cooking is 3,82 kWh, a value that corresponds with the above mentioned data (Riofrio, 2015).

In the case of LPG stoves, previous studies show a typical daily consumption of 8,85 kWh, and a monthly consumption of 265,39 kWh (Riofrio, 2015), (CONELEC, 2013), which translates into 17,6 kg of LPG per month. In Ecuador the bottled gas capacity is 15 kg, therefore the average household needs 1,13 bottles per month for its cooking activities. The sum of energy consumption with LPG stoves cooking of six dishes in this study is 15,64 kWh, a rate well above the 8,85 kWh reported before. This is because in order to conduct this study, the industrial stove was adapted to simulate a families stove, reducing the maximum power of it, which affects the efficiency as well.

Under these considerations it is possible to estimate the primary energy consumption for cooking activities of an Ecuadorian family in the current scenario, and in 2022 by the kind of stove employed. For the LPG stove a primary energy factor of 1,05 has been considered (IDAE, 2011), resulting in 278,66 kWh a month, which is the same for both scenarios 2014 and 2022. For the calculation of the inductions stove factor, the primary energy depends on the electricity production mix, which varies from 2014 to 2022, as shown in Table 1. The primary energy monthly consumption by a family cooking with induction stoves is 156,29 kWh in 2014, and will be reduced to 114,93 kWh in 2022, if the new hydroelectric power station and the electric grid transmission infrastructure are built.

3.3 Costs scenarios for the government and families

Today Ecuador consumes about 11454 GWh of primary energy for cooking activities annually. The governments annual subsidy lays on 847,96 Mus\$ for bottled gas LPG stoves, and less than 0,4 Mus\$ for induction stoves. In the business as usual scenario (BAU), where there are no active policies to introduce more induction stoves and the subsidy to LPG remains as nowadays, the energy subsidy costs to the state budget would increase to around 1184,47 Mus\$ annually for the LPG stoves, and 0,54 Mus\$ for induction stoves. The primary energy consumption for cooking activities in BAU 2022 scenario would increase to 16000 GWh annually. The other way around, if the new policy scenario for 2022, the NECP reach 4688795 induction stoves running, the primary energy consumption would drop to around 6142,4 GWh annually. In this case, the budget for energy subsidy for cooking activities would decrease to 20,01 Mus\$ annually, supporting induction stoves exclusively, since the subsidy for bottled LPG concludes in this scenario. These results are resumed in Table 3.

Table 3. Scenarios of global energy consumption for both technologies

	Units	2014		2022			
		16026220,3		18044656			
		Current situation		Business as Usual		New policies	
		GLP	Induction	GLP	Induction	GLP	Induction
N° of Stoves	[U]	3407375	50000	4759570	70029	140804	4688795
Monthly consumption	[GWh]	904,28	4,80	1263,14	6,72	37,37	450,12
Annual consumption	[GWh]	10851,40	57,60	15157,71	80,67	448,41	5401,49
Primary energy	[GWh]	11393,97	60,48	15915,59	84,71	470,83	5671,57
Cost	[M\$us]	921,70	5,30	1287,47	5,21	38,09	348,8
Subsidy cost	[M\$us]	847,96	0,37	1184,47	0,54	0	20,01
Total primary energy	[GWh]	11454,45		16000,30		6142,4	
Total cost	[M\$us]	927,00		1292,68		386,89	
Subsidy cost	[M\$us]	848,33		1184,78		20,01	

Table 4 shows the scenario of the monthly and annual energy consumption of a typical Ecuadorian family with both technologies. Assuming that the costs for the families today according to the type of fuel, result in a monthly energy cost of 21,64 us\$ for LPG and 17,66 us\$ for induction stoves electricity. In this scope, the state is subsidizing 248,86 us\$ for LPG stoves and 88,32 us\$ for induction stoves for each family every year. Removing subsidies on LPG in 2022, and with the policy of the NECP (MEER., 2013), a family will spend 270,50 us\$ for cooking with LPG and 57,14 us\$ for cooking with induction stoves every month.

Table 4. Monthly and annual energy consumption scenario for a typical ecuadorian family for both technologies

	Units	Current situation 2014		Future situation (2022)	
		GLP	Induction	GLP	Induction
Monthly consumption	[kWh]	265,39	96	265,39	96
Annual consumption	[kWh]	3184,68	1152	3184,68	1152
Total cost per year	[us\$]	270,50	105,98	270,50	70,85
Subsidy cost per year	[us\$]	248,86	88,32	0	13,71
User cost per year	[us\$]	21,64	17,66	270,50	57,14

* The first 80 kWh are not paid and the rate is 0.092 us\$.

** The rate of the first 80 kWh is \$0.04 and above the rate: 0.0615 us\$.

4 Discussion

This research reveals the effect/impact of the implementation of the National Efficiency Cooking Program, which is a vanguard policy that resolves the access to clean cooking activities and the costs of high state subsidies at a national level. The NECP aims the household migration from LPG based stoves to induction stoves. That success is based on a strong administrative, technical, and outreach competence. Accessible resources available at the local level and motivation by sustained national-level attention are required (Sinton et al., 2004). This is the first policy that has been issued with this level of implementation worldwide. Recently, a pilot program for introducing 4000 induction

stoves in rural households in Himachal Pradesh has been implemented (Banerjee, 2016). Unlike the NECP though, this program is not accompanied by a change on the energy mix, neither considers the households at a national level such as in the case of Ecuador.

Regarding to CO and CO₂ emissions, a test of both gases in the three different types of stoves was performed. A considerable increment of CO and CO₂ concentrations during the frying process has been observed. Similar results were obtained by (Dennekamp et al., 2001; Abdullahi et al., 2013; Buonanno et al., 2011), In contrast, (He et al., 2004) and (Zhao et al., 2014), did not detect/perceive this correlation between the frying process and the increment of CO and CO₂ concentrations. Furthermore, CO₂ and CO emissions of the LPG stove were observed to settle between 1000 to 10000 ppm, and from 3 to 20 ppm respectively. Similar results were detected in the investigation of (Zhao, 2014). In addition, the results show that the emission of CO and CO₂ not only relate to the cooking time, but also remain longer in the environment as a result of the burning of the LPG. Consequently, when higher calorific power is used in the LPG stove during cooking activities, a higher level of CO₂ is generated. These results are correlated with the research developed by (Kumar et al., 2014) with typical meals from Nigeria. The maximum obtained emission of CO and CO₂ during the frying process of Nigerian dishes using LPG, is at least between 54 % and 117% higher respectively, than when using boiling procedures, exceeding the maximum level of volatile emissions acceptable in buildings and indoor environments (Indoor Air Quality Standard of China (GB/T 18883), 2002; Koistinen et al., 2001; Sehjpal et al., 2014). On the other hand, electrical coil and induction stoves kept the concentration of CO and CO₂ within the acceptable level during the cooking process.

According to the time and energy consumption for processing the six experimental meals in the induction stove as a reference, the electric coil stove increases the cooking time in a 96 % and the energy consumption in a 28 %. The LPG stove increases the time consumption in 61 %, and the energy consumption in 309 %. This time reduction is based in most of the cases to step 2 and 3 of appendix 2, which corresponds to the heating processes of water or oil.

Within the current situation, the annual total amount of money spent for the energy consumption by LPG based stoves presented in Table 3 is 921,70 Mus\$ (with subsidizes), which represent 57,51 us\$ per capita. While the annual total expenses for the energy consumption by induction stoves is 5,3 Mus\$, which means 0,33 us\$ per capita. For the BAU2022 scenario, the annual total amount spent for energy consumption by LPG based stoves is 1287,47 Mus\$, which represent 71,35 us\$ per capita in 2022. Meanwhile the annual total expenses in BAU scenario 2022 for energy consumption by induction stoves is 5,21 Mus\$, which represent 0,29 us\$ per capita. At last, within the future new policy scenario presented in Table 3, the annual total amount spent for energy consumption by LPG based stoves is 38,09 Mus\$, which represent 2,11 us\$ per capita. While the annual total expenses for the energy consumption by induction stoves is 348,8 Mus\$, which represent 19,33 us\$ per capita.

Today the government is subsidizing the energy for cooking with 52,93 us\$ per capita and year, mainly in bottled LPG, a fuel that the government has to import. If new policies are not considered, the BAU2022 scenario reveals that the government will need to invest subsidies of 65,66 us\$ per capita and year, again in dependency on imported LPG. However with the implementation of the NEPC, the new policies 2022 scenario shows that the cooking energy subsidy will reduced to 1,11 us\$ per year per capita. This subsidy would specifically sustain a local energy source as the hydropower infrastructure station, a situation that is already being implemented nowadays. Also in 2022 the primary energy consumption for cooking in Ecuador will increase to 40% the actual value, which is from

11454,45 GWh, to 16000,3 GWh. Though if new policies of technological migration are implemented, the primary energy consumption will decrease to 51% as considered in the NEPC, to 6142,4 GWh.

The energy subsidy costs for the government will be 98% less for 2022 (in the new policies 2022scenario), than the actual subsidy budget for cooking nowadays. This reduction will be absorbed by the final user, who now is spending 21,64us\$ per year, and will increase its energy costs for cooking to 57,14 us\$ per year. Without the NEPC, the user that keeps cooking with LPG in 2022 would pay 270,50 us\$ per year. So, under the NEPC, increasing 2,6 times the cooking energy costs per family (would be 12,5 times without NEPC), together with the technological transition from LPG to induction stoves, and the investment in local hydropower electricity facilities, leads to a reduction of 42,4 times the energy subsidy budget for cooking to the Ecuadorian government.

In the context of the micro economic analysis for the representative Ecuadorian family, it is essential to consider that the annual costs of vital products for 2014 was 7548,12 us\$, and the minimum wage was about 4080,00 us\$ (INEC, 2014). Today cooking with LPG stoves implies 0,28 % of the basic food basket costs and 0,53 % of the minimum wage, while for cooking with induction stoves these values are 0,23% and 0,43% respectively. The minimum wage is expected to rise for 2022, but for reference calculations it will be considered fixed. So, the increase of energy cooking costs for a family in 2022 using induction stoves, with the introduction of the NEPC, will imply 0,76 % of the basic food basket costs and 1,4% of the minimum wage. While cooking with LPG stoves will imply 3,58 % of the basic food basket costs and 6,63 % of the minimum wage.

5 Conclusions and policy implications

The technological migration for cooking in Ecuador considering the NEPC policies, accompanied by the introduction of new hydropower facilities in the country, has been analyzed. The CO₂ and CO emissions when cooking typical Ecuadorian meals in LPG stoves are higher than those recommended as healthy, while when cooking with electric stoves (coil and induction) these values are in a safe range. The induction stove shows a better performance in comparison to the LPG or electric coil stoves, reducing the energy consumption and the time required for cooking activities. If new policies are not implemented and the LPG subsidy is maintained, in 2022 the budget for the cooking energy subsidy in Ecuador will increase up to 40% in comparison to the current budget, reaching more than 1000 Mus\$ per year. While the implementation of new policies considered in the NEPC with massive introduction of induction stoves, leads to a reduction of 98% in the cooking energy subsidy budget in comparison to the current budget (see Table 3).A representative family will increase its energy costs for cooking with induction stoves (instead current LPG subsidized ones) in 2,6 times, aside from health benefits. If in 2022 the families keep cooking with LPG, when LPG subsidy is removed, the costs for cooking would turn around 12,5 times higher than nowadays

Therefore, the policy that Ecuador is implementing to reach a clean cooking scenario by the introduction of induction stoves, that is provided with new local hydropower facilities, and replaces in this manner LPG stoves and the import of a fossil fuel which is currently subsidized, would lead to a better performance in the government's budget, improvement of energy sovereignty, security and health benefits for families (mainly women and children), and would represent a real alternative to the conclusion of the LPG subsidy, sharing the economic impact of this measure with the country's population.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1. The essential information of each meal.

Dishes	Ingredients	Quantity	Treatment	Picture	Description
Chicken broth	Chicken Green beans Carrot Turnip Coriander Green onion Garlic Rice "Chola" Potato Water	430 g 100 g 100 g 50 g 6 g 15 g 5 g 50 g 300 g 2 l	Cut in pieces. Washed. Cut in tiny cubes. Cut in tiny cubes. Chopped. Chopped. Chopped.		This soup is well-known in Latin America, especially in Ecuador. It is a typical soup that contains ingredients such as potatoes, carrots and turnip among others. This soup is usually prepared as a home remedy for colds.
Cheese and potato soup	Potato Cheese Milk Green onion Achiote oil Butter Coriander Water Salt Pepper	600 g 125 g 250 g 50 g 25 g 30 g 5 g 1.5 l Salt Pepper	Cut in slices. Cute in cubes. Chopped. Chopped.		A very popular soup in the Ecuadorian highlands, especially in the city of Quito and the northern provinces of Ecuador. It is characterized by being served accompanied by avocado and cheese pieces.
Quinoa soup	Quinoa Pork ribs Green onion "Chola" Potato Garlic Achiote oil White cabbage Coriander Water	150 g 227 g 30 g 200 g 5 g 20 g 50 g 5 g 1.5 l	Washed. Chunks. Thin chopped. Cut in cubes. Chopped. Strips. Chopped.		This is a typical soup of the Andean countries. Quinoa is characterized of being healthy and a high protein cereal. In addition, this soup is a delicious antidote to cold climates.
Barley rice soup	Barley rice Pork ribs Green onion "Chola" Potato Garlic Achiote oil White cabbage Coriander Water	150 g 227 g 250 g 200 g 5 g 20 g 50 g 5 g 1.5 l	Washed. Chunks. Chopped. Cut in cubes. Chopped. Strips. Chopped.		A traditional soup of highland provinces of Ecuador, especially in Pichincha (province of Quito) and Carchi. It is characterized by a high nutritional content, therefore convenient for feeding children.
White rice	Rice Water Sal	250 g 660 g 5 g	Washed.		Rice is the staple food of over half the world's population. It is the predominant dietary energy source for 17 countries in Asia and the Pacific, 9 countries in North and South America and 8 countries in Africa. Rice provides 20% of the world's dietary energy supply.
French fries	Potatoes Oil Salt	400 g 1 l 5 g	Chopped		French fries are served hot, either soft or crispy, and generally eaten as part of lunch or dinner, or on their own as a snack. They commonly appear on the menus of fast food restaurants. French fries are generally salted and are often served with ketchup; in many countries they are topped instead with other condiments and toppings, including vinegar, mayonnaise, or other local spices.

Appendix 2. Cooking process information

Dishes	Cooking process	Energy Cost induction stove [\$]	Energy Cost Electric coil stove [\$]	*Energy Cost LPG stove [\$]
Chicken broth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Turn on the stove with a high heat. • Step 2: Add and boil the water. • Step 3: Incorporate the chicken to the soup. • Step 4: Incorporate the green beans, carrot, coriander, turnip, and garlic. • Step 5: Incorporate the rice and the “chola” potatoes. • Step 6: Incorporate the green onion. • Step 7: Turn off the stove. 	0,079	0,081	0,245
Cheese and potato soup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Turn on the stove. • Step 2: Fry the green onion with achiote oil and butter. • Step 3: Add water, salt and paper and boil the soup. • Step 4: Incorporate the slices of potatoes. • Step 5: Boil milk for 3 min and add it to the soup. • Step 6: Add the cheese. • Step 7: Add the coriander. • Step 8: Turn off the stove. 	0,066	0,101	0,256
Quinoa soup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Turn on the stove. • Step 2: Fry the pork ribs with achiote oil. • Step 3: Add the green onion and garlic. • Step 4: Add water and boil. • Step 5: Add quinoa. • Step 6: Add potatoes. • Step 7: Incorporate the white cabbage. • Step 8: Add the coriander. • Step 9: Turn off the stove. 	0,047	0,062	0,236
Barley rice soup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Turn on the stove. • Step 2: Fry the pork ribs with achiote oil. • Step 3: Fry the green onion and the garlic with pork ribs. • Step 4: Add water and boil. • Step 5: Add the barley rice and boil. • Step 6: Add “chola” potatoes and white cabbage and boil. • Step 7: Add the coriander. • Step 8: Turn off the stove. 	0,54	0,082	0,241
White rice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Turn on the stove. • Step 2: Add and boil the water. • Step 3: Incorporate the rice and boil • Step 4: Turn off the stove. 	0,036	0,097	0,172
French fries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Turn on the stove. • Step 2: Add and fry the olive oil. • Step 3: Incorporate the potatoes and fry • Step 4: Turn off the stove. 	0,022	0,041	0,101

* For this analysis the price of a LPG bottled gas of 15 kg without subsidy, \$20.00 has been considered